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East Tapinac, Olongapo City

College of Computer Studies

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Worksheet 1

Title: Arduino Basics – Dual LED Control

Objective(s):

- Recognize Arduino UNO digital pins.
- Demonstrate digital output by controlling 2 LEDs.
- Compare timing patterns with different delays.

Instructions:

- Connect 2 LEDs (with 220 Ω resistors) to pins 12 and 13.
- Upload code: LED1 blinks ON while LED2 is OFF, alternating.
- Test with delays of 1000 ms, 700 ms, and 300 ms.

Data Gathering:

Trial	Delay (ms)	LED1 Behavior	Behavior	Notes
1	1000	LED1 ON/OFF every 1 sec	LED2 ON when LED1 OFF	Pattern was slow and easy to follow
2	700	LED1 ON/OFF every 0.7 sec	LED2 ON when LED1 OFF	Blink rate faster, still distinguishable
3	300	LED1 ON/OFF every 0.3 sec	LED2 ON when LED1 OFF	Very fast blink, harder to track with

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Observation: The two LEDs alternated properly in all trials, and the change in delay clearly affected the blink speed, with faster delays making the blinking more difficult to follow visually.

Conclusion & Recommendation: The experiment successfully demonstrated dual LED control using Arduino digital pins with alternating timing.

Image1: Circuit Diagram

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Code:

```
// Define LED pins
const int LED1 = 12;
const int LED2 = 13;

// Set delay time (you can test with 1000, 700, and 200 ms)
int delayTime = 1000; // Change to 700 or 200 as needed

void setup() {
  // Set both LED pins as output
  pinMode(LED1, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(LED2, OUTPUT);
}

void loop() {
  // Turn LED1 ON, LED2 OFF
  digitalWrite(LED1, HIGH);
  digitalWrite(LED2, LOW);
  delay(delayTime);

  // Turn LED1 OFF, LED2 ON
  digitalWrite(LED1, LOW);
  digitalWrite(LED2, HIGH);
  delay(delayTime);
}
```

Extension Task: Try to make both LEDs blink together after alternating.